

maintainer line and pollen source was planted in a 3- × 3-m plot at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The cytotsterile line was planted at 30- × 20-cm spacing in 5 rows on each side of the pollen-source plot. The 1st row of 10 plants was 30 cm from the pollen source; the 2d, 50; the 3d, 70; the 4th, 90; and the 5th, 110.

One primary panicle of each male sterile plant was bagged before flowering. The others remained uncovered for natural outcrossing. The flag leaf was clipped for supplementary pollination.

At maturity, V20A plants were harvested individually and seed set was

counted to determine the extent of outcrossing. The bagged panicles did not set any seed, but seed set on uncovered panicles varied with the direction of planting and distance to the pollen source (see table). Low seed set probably was caused by poor V20A panicle exertion. *ℒ*

Isolation of maintainers and restorers for three different male sterile lines

S. N. Ratho and K. Pande, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Thirty-six early- and medium-duration rice, (33 improved Indian varieties and 3

Restorers and maintainers for V20A, Wu 10A, and Pankhari 203A male sterile lines at CRRI, Cuttack, India.^a

Variety	V20A	Wu 10A	Pankhari 203A
Pallavi	M	PR	WM
Gaur-1	WM	PR	M
IR30	-	M	M
Karuna	PR	WM	PR
IR36	R	M	PR
Karjat 184	R	WM	PR
Vani	R	WM	M
Rasi	WM	PR	-
Bharathi	M	WM	PR
IR50	R	PR	PR
Indira	-	WM	M
Palman 579	-	WM	WM
Kanchan	-	WM	WM
Pusa 33	R	PR	M
Prabhat	-	PR	M
Pushpa	-	M	M
Sita	-	M	-
Aswathi	R	PR	WM
Sona	-	PR	M
Palghat 60	PR	WM	-
Pragati	-	M	-
Prasad	R	M	-
Vaigai	-	WM	-
CR190-103	-	M	M
Rajeswari	M	M	M
Kranti	PR	PR	PR
MW10	M	PR	M
Kumar	PR	WM	M
Ratnagiri	-	PR	M
Gaur-10	PR	-	PR
Krishna	M	PR	-
Archana	M	WM	M
Madhu	M	WM	WM
Jamuna	-	M	WM
Karikalan	WM	-	M
Ratna	PR	-	WM

^aR= restorer (80 to 100% spikelet fertility); PR = partial restorer (20 to 80% spikelet fertility); WM = weak maintainer (5 to 20% spikelet fertility); M = maintainer (0 to 5% spikelet fertility); - = damaged seedlings.

from IRRI) were crossed as male parents with each of 3 cytoplasmic, genetic sterile lines — V20A, Wu 10A, and Pankhari 203A — to identify their maintainers and restorers. The F₁ hybrids were grown in the field and in pots in a greenhouse. The main panicles of each plant were bagged and percent spikelet fertility was estimated.

Varieties were classified as effective restorers (>8% spikelet fertility), weak or partial restorers (20 to 80%), weak maintainers (5 to 20%), and effective maintainers (<5%).

IR36, IR50, Karjat 184, Vani, Pusa 33, Aswathi, and Prasad were effective restorers for V20A and Pallavi, Bharathi, Rajeswari, MW 10, Krishna, Archana, and Madhu were effective maintainers (see table). None of the varieties were effective restorers for Wu

10A, but IR30, IR36, Pushpa, Sita, Pragati, Prasad, CR190-103, Rajeswari, and Jamuna were effective maintainers. Similarly, no effective restorers were identified for Pankhari 203A, but 15 were effective maintainers.

IR30, Pushpa, and CR190-103 were maintainers for both Wu 10A and Pankhari 203A. MW 10 and Archana were both maintainers for V20A and Pankhari 203A. Rajeswari was a maintainer for all the three male sterile lines.

IR36 and Prasad were restorers for V20A and maintainers for Wu 10A. Similarly, Vani and Pusa 33 were restorers for V20A and maintainers for Pankhari 203A. The results indicate that the cytoplasm of the three male sterile lines interact differently in the pollinator varieties used in this study. *ℒ*

Pedigree of AR-11 series, upland rices of northeast India

T. C. Chaudhuri, Tea Board, Darjeeling Tea Research Centre, Kurseong 734203, India

Juming is a traditional rice cultivation system used by tribes in the northeastern hills of India. No systematic breeding program had attempted to improve local varieties, although some plains varieties were introduced. Although collection, screening, and selection of upland germplasm at Arundhuti Nagar Research Station at Agarthala in Tripura did not produce significant results, several hybridizations were attempted. The AR-11 series was developed and became popular. Now, AR-11 varieties are widely planted.

Narkeljuri is a local tall (120 cm) upland rice of Tripura; susceptible to

lodging, blast (Bl), and *Helminthosporium* diseases; and low tillering (1 to 2). It has light green, narrow, long boot leaves, and genes for cluster grains; is photoperiod sensitive, and moderately tolerant of moisture stress; matures in 110 d (May-Jul); and yields 0.8 t/ha. It was crossed with semidwarf high yielding Bala, a South India variety.

The F₁ had intermediate idiosyncrasy, was almost sterile (5% of the embryos developed), and multiplied by repeated cloning.

Only 20 F₂ plants grew. The F₂ progeny was highly sterile and segregated widely for plant height (90 to 140 cm), leaf length and color (dark to light green), leaf pose (drooping, semierect to erect), pigmentation (absent, light to dark), number of tillers (1 to 10), spikelet characters, and cluster grains (1 to 10/cluster).